

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Diphenylcarbazide and Diphenylcarbazone : Part-IV.

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1,5-Diphenylcarbohydrazide- $C_6H_5NHNHCONHNHC_6H_5$ (RH_4) is a well known colorimetric reagent for the estimation of chromium. But the products responsible for the colouration could not be isolated. It has been shown¹ by spectrophotometric titration of RH_4 with Cr (VI), at least three species exist reacting in the molar ratios Cr (VI) : RH_4 as 2 : 15, 2 : 3 and 8 : 9. Now a product has been isolated from the reaction mixture in the ratio 8 : 9.

The reaction was made in aqueous acetone containing dilute H_2SO_4 . After filtration the acid was neutralised with $MgCO_3$ and the filtrate was concentrated at temperatures below 40° by vacuum evaporation and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 . The dried mass was well-triturated with water and the water-washed residue, after being dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 , was extracted with dry acetone and the acetone extract was treated with excess of dry ether when a partial separation of the coloured species took place. It was collected and the process was repeated twice more. Finally the acetone extract was treated with petroleum ether (b.p. $40^\circ-60^\circ$) for immediate separation of the product. It was then washed with petroleum ether and dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . Analytical results show that the compound may be regarded as $[Cr(RH)(OH)(H_2O)_3]_2SO_4$. [Found : Cr, 12.80; N, 13.96; S, 3.75; RH_2 , 58.60; calc : Cr, 12.68; N, 13.66; S, 3.90; RH_2 , 58.53%]. $RH_2 = 1, 5$ -diphenylcarbazone ($C_6H_5N=NCONHNHC_6H_5$) was estimated following the method² introduced by us and $-RH$ may be $C_6H_5N=NCON-NHC_6H_5$ or $C_6H_5N=N-C=N-NHC_6H_5$.

Magnetic data-found $\mu_B = 3.75$ B.M. at 26° —indicate that chromium in the compound has (d^3) configuration and obviously is in the tripositive state. Absorption spectra in $0.2(N)H_2SO_4$ show peak at $540 m\mu$ having extinction coefficient per chromium = 19,900. It is necessary to mention here that absorption spectra of 1 : 10 mixture or solutions containing large excess of RH_4 in $0.2(N)H_2SO_4$ show peak also at $540 m\mu$ but having the extinction coefficient per chromium = 40,300 (found in the literature³—40,000).

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